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**International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies
Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) Conference**

13 – 15 September 2023

Istanbul, Turkey

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Preface

On behalf of the organizing committee, I would like to welcome all participants and speakers to the International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) Conference in Istanbul/Turkiye. This conference is the first international conference under Cost Action 20133: Cross Border Transfer and Development of Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) and I hope it will be the starting point for a series of FULLRECO4US conferences. It is my pleasure to thank COST Action 20133 (funded by the European Union) for their financial support.

FULLRECO4US Istanbul 2023 conference provides a unique opportunity for professionals from around the world to learn, share and present the latest knowledge and insights on circular economy, zero waste, resource recovery strategies, energy resources and sustainable food systems. The conference is a networking platform with the world's leading experts in resource recovery strategies and related fields. It is an important event for assessing the key challenges in promoting a sustainable zero waste bringing together an international community of leading academics, researchers, engineers and industry professionals to exchange and share their ideas and experiences.

This conference was organized in Istanbul by Innobrane Research Group led by Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer and Bilig Upcycling Academy. The local organizing team, which are members of Innobrane Research Group, consists of Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer (conference chair), Sama Al-Mutwalli (conference secretariat), Tugba Sapmaz-Wikstrom (conference secretariat), Mustafa Taher (conference secretariat), Elifnur Gezmis Yavuz, Esra Buyukada Kesici, Feyza Nur Buyuknalçaci, Sezer Gençturk, Yasin Sahin, Duygu Tozaraydin, Cagri Kaan Kilic. There was also an international organizing committee composed of 10 members from 9 different countries: Mohammad Taherzadeh (SE), Philippe Corvini (CH), Pieter Billen (BE), Olga Nunes (PT), Jorge Marchetti (NO), Patrik Lennartsson (SE), Timo Kikas (EE), Belen Garcia (ES), Gjore Nakov (BG), Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer (TR). The scientific committee of the conference included 120 reviewers from 36 countries. We had 2 plenary speakers, 7 keynote speakers, 7 stakeholders, 57 oral presentations, and 51 poster presentations and more than 200 participants from 35 countries. The conference showed a good balance in terms of gender equality: 57% of the participants were women and 43% were men.

It is my pleasure to thank Prof. Mohammad J. Taherzadeh (COST Action Chair) and all members of the core group and management committee of COST Action-20133, members of local organizing team, all participants, stakeholders, Kolektif House, Bilig Academy and Crowlink who contributed to success of this conference.

Istanbul is truly a crossroads of ideas and cultures between Europe and Asia. I hope that all participants had good memories of the FULLRECO4US Istanbul Conference.

See you again in Istanbul, Sincerely

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer (Conference Chair)

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Properties of biowaste-derived hydrochar as a tool for various environmental applications

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Abstract

Providing enough food for the growing population is accompanied by an increase in the generation of biodegradable agri-food waste. In Serbia, a significant amount of agri-food waste is produced (around 13.8 million tons per year), but only 16.8% of total biodegradable waste is recycled [1].

Two effects can be achieved by valorizing biomass and raising awareness of its importance as a resource: reducing the content of existing biowaste and obtaining new functional products. One of the products obtained by re-using waste biomass is hydrochar (HC), a carbon material obtained through the hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) process, with unique properties suitable for diverse environmental applications. The production process entails the HTC of both dry and wet feedstocks. HTC takes place in relatively mild process conditions (180-250 °C and 2-22 MPa) in the presence of water in a subcritical state, where, in addition to HC, process water and gases are separated.

The properties and yield of HC depend on several factors, such as the type of biomass used, the reaction temperature, and the residence time. When the production takes place at high temperatures (e.g. > 200°C), a low yield of char occurs, but a high carbon conversion is achieved, resulting in chars with high heating value. HC from lignocellulosic biomass has high total carbon content (38-91%) and low ash content (up to 13%). During HTC performed in an aqueous medium, the oxidative functional groups form on the surface of char. HC from agro biowaste has a high specific surface area and pore volume, which can be further improved through activation/functionalization.

Exceptional surface area, porosity, and functional groups make HC useful soil amendments, fertilizers, adsorbents, and renewable energy sources. HC is an effective biosorbent for organic pollutants and heavy metals removal from water, as well as for soil remediation [2]. Utilizing waste biomass for hydrochar production aligns with circular economy principles and promotes sustainable agriculture. This study will contribute to unlocking the potential of HC for a greener and more sustainable future.

[1] http://www.sepa.gov.rs/download/IZVESTAJ_2021.pdf;

[2] A. Khosravi, H. Zheng, Q. Liu, M. Hashemi, Y. Tang, B. Xing, Production and characterization of hydrochars and their application in soil improvement and environmental remediation, Chemical Engineering Journal, Volume 430, 2022, 133142, ISSN 1385-8947.